

THE ROLE OF DISCOURSE ANALYSIS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: At the present stage, in teaching a foreign language, tasks aimed at the formation of communicative and discursive competencies that contribute to the achievement of the most important goal, consisting in the formation of a secondary linguistic personality, who are able to fully communicate in this language, become especially relevant. These competencies become especially significant when it comes to the use of literary texts in the training of future philologists and translators.

Keywords: discourse analyses, discursive competencies, foreign language, literary text, pragmatics, semiotics, linguistics, informatics.

INTRODUCTION

According to our research, in the second half of the twentieth century, at the intersection of several sciences: hermeneutics, sociology, pragmatics, semiotics, linguistics, informatics, rhetoric, psychology, it emerged as a scientific discipline - the theory of text, known in European science under the term "theory of discourse". It, regardless of the number of interdisciplinary intersections, has a full-fledged individual ontological status and includes any sequence of signs. It is worth noting that its main object is a verbal text, in this regard, the data accumulated in linguistics in the process of describing and characterizing the text are important.

Discourse analysis is a fairly broad concept that refers to the process of learning how language is used in different texts and contexts, or in texts that accompany or even define discourse itself. In academia, the term discourse analysis became widespread in the 1970s. According to the definition given by Abrams and Harfam [1, p. 48] in the Glossary of Literary Terms, this term is associated with "the use of language in fluent discourse, continuing over a series of sentences and involving the interaction of the speaker (writer) and auditor (reader) in a particular situational context and within the framework of specific social and cultural conventions".

In contrast to grammatical analysis, which focuses on a singular sentence, discourse analysis, by contrast, focuses on the wide and common use of language within and between specific groups of people. In addition, grammarians usually construct examples themselves, which are subsequently

analyzed, while discourse analysis relies on the speech (oral and written) results of the works of a large number of people, as the goal is to identify the popular uses of the language.

METHODOLOGY

The methods and concepts of recent study of discourse make possible an analysis of the discourses, in their relation to institutional practices, through which a division of texts has been marked out and literature has been constituted as the object of a certain enshrinement.

For at least ten years now discourse has been a fashionable term. In scientific texts and debates, it is used indiscriminately, often without being defined. The concept has become vague, either meaning almost nothing, or being used with more precise, but rather different, meanings in different contexts. But, in many cases, underlying the word discourse is the general idea that language is structured according to different patterns that people's utterances follow when they take part in different domains of social life, familiar examples being medical discourse and political discourse.

Discourse analysis is the analysis of the set patterns. But this common sense definition is not of much help in clarifying what discourses are, how they function, or how to analyze them. Here, more developed theories and methods of discourse analysis have to be sought out. And, in the search, one quickly finds out that discourse analysis is not just one approach, but a series of interdisciplinary approaches that can be used to explore many different social domains in many different types of studies. And there is no clear consensus as to what discourses are or how to analyze them. Different perspectives offer their own suggestions and, to some extent, compete to appropriate the terms discourse and discourse analysis for their own definitions. Let us begin, however, by proposing the preliminary definition of a discourse as a particular way of talking about and understanding the world (or an aspect of the world).

LITERATURE REVIEW

G. Brown and G. Yule [2, p. 24] note that in "discourse analysis" the field for research is rarely formed on the basis of one sentence (or even on the basis of one text). For their observations, the authors of discourse analysis should, first of all, collect the required amount of data - in our case - text units. Then, find in audio recordings or handwritten texts, such phenomena such as the specificity of each text,

common features and similarity of the text with other texts, non-standard forms in the studied text and their correspondence to the semantic load. In

simple terms, this means that discourse analysis is about observing spoken, cultural, and actual use of a language, while grammar analysis relies entirely on sentence structure, word use, and stylistic choices at the sentence level, which can often include culture. but not the human element of discourse.

Michael Stubbs (1983) treats text and discourse as more or less synonymous, but notes that in other usages a text may be written, while a discourse is spoken, a text may be no interactive whereas a discourse is interactive a text may be short or long whereas a discourse implies a certain length, and a text must be possessed of surface cohesion whereas a discourse must be possessed of a deeper coherence. Finally, Stubbs notes that other theorists distinguish between abstract theoretical construct and pragmatic realization, although, confusingly, such theorists are not agreed upon which of these is represented by the term text. (Hawthorn, 1992: 189; emphasis in original)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sentence, an undefined creation of limitless variety, is the very life of human speech in action. We conclude from this that with the sentence we leave the domain of language as a system of signs and enter into another universe, that of language as an instrument of communication, whose expression is discourse.

Three different approaches to social constructionist discourse analysis – Ernesto Laclau and Chantal Mouffe’s discourse theory, critical discourse analysis, and discursive psychology. All three approaches share the starting point that our ways of talking do not neutrally reflect our world, identities and social relations but, rather, play an active role in creating and changing them. We have selected these approaches from the range of different perspectives within discourse analysis on the grounds that we think that they represent particularly fruitful theories and methods for research in communication, culture and society. They can be applied in analysis of many different social domains, including organizations and institutions, and in exploration of the role of language use in broad societal and cultural developments such as globalization and the spread of mass mediated communication...Michel Foucault has played a central role in the development of discourse analysis through both theoretical work and empirical research.

In almost all discourse analytical approaches, Foucault has become a figure to quote, relate to, comment on, modify and criticize. We will also touch on Foucault, sketching out his areas of contribution to discourse analysis – not

only in order to live up to the implicit rules of the game, but also because all our approaches have roots in Foucault's ideas, while rejecting some parts of his theory. Some approaches focus on the fact that discourses are created and changed in everyday discursive practices and therefore stress the need for systematic empirical analyses of people's talk and written language in, for instance, the mass media or research interviews. Other approaches are more concerned with general, overarching patterns and aim at a more abstract mapping of the discourses that circulate in society at a particular moment in time or within a specific social domain. The study of discourse does not differentiate between those texts which are designated as literary and those which are designated as non-literary, although discourse theorists are keenly aware of the institutionalized differences that exist between the two sets of texts. History texts are privileged in their relation to truth, for example; autobiographical writings are privileged in terms of their supposed authenticity in relation to an authorial voice; and literary texts have a complex relation to both truth and value, on the one hand being seen as providing a truth about the human condition, and yet doing so within a fictional and therefore untrue form. However, for the discussion of the construction, say, of discourses of femininity and masculinity, it is possible to discuss literary texts alongside other texts, such as works of history and autobiography, and even more ephemeral texts, such as cookery books, advice manuals and so on, in order to reveal the similarities these texts display across generic boundaries. Discourse is therefore useful in that it can allow us to analyse similarities across a range of texts as the products of a particular set of power/ knowledge relations.

Discourse theory aims at an understanding of the social as a discursive construction whereby, in principle, all social phenomena can be analyzed using discourse analytical tools. First, we present the discourse theoretical approach to language, and then extend the theory to cover the entire social field. Because of its broad focus, discourse theory is suitable as a theoretical foundation for different social constructionist approaches to discourse analysis. But since Laclau and Mouffe's texts aim at theory development, they do not include so many practical tools for textually oriented discourse analysis. As a result, it can be fruitful to supplement their theory with methods from other approaches to discourse analysis.

The pedagogic consequence of this new functional perspective is that language and communication are placed in a wider framework. They can no longer be defined as pedagogic aims in themselves, but as a means of adaptation and

survival in the world. Another consequence is that, if the choice of a specific lexical-grammatical structure is presented as one level of adaptation, side by side with other levels (choice of pronunciation, style, situation, channel, function), we should start thinking of distributing our teaching efforts accordingly, instead of giving grammar so much priority over the other levels.

Using a foreign language is very often synonymous with participating in an intercultural communicative event, where the risk of misunderstanding increases because the interlocutors do not share the same cultural values and have different expectations about how to do things with language. In this situation, the negotiation of meaning has an even more important role than in intracultural communication.

To attain a good command of a foreign language learners should either be exposed to it in genuine circumstances and with natural frequency, or painstakingly study lexis and syntax assuming that students have some contact with natural input. Classroom discourse seems to be the best way of systematizing the linguistic code that learners are to acquire. The greatest opportunity to store, develop and use the knowledge about the target language is arisen by exposure to authentic discourse in the target language provided by the teacher. Language is not only the aim of education as it is in the case of teaching English to Polish students, but also the means of schooling by the use of mother tongue. Having realized that discourse analysts attempted to describe the role and importance of language in both contexts simultaneously paying much attention to possible improvement to be made in these fields.

It has also been settled that what is essential to be successful in language learning is interaction, in both written and spoken form. In addition, students "failures in communication which result in negotiation of meaning, requests for explanation or reorganization of message contribute to language acquisition. One of the major concerns of discourse analysts has been the manner in which students ought to be involved in the learning process, how to control turn-taking, provide feedback as well a show to teach different skills most effectively on the grounds of discourse analysis" offerings conversation takes his turn to speak to link his utterance to what has been said before.

CONCLUSION

In recent years, discourse analysis has evolved in parallel with rhetorical research in order to include a much wider range of topics, from mass to private use of language, from official to spoken rhetoric, and from oratory to written and multimedia discourse. According to K. Eisenhart and B. Johnston, discourse

analysis and analysis of rhetoric have similar goals, since they allow analyzing texts from the point of view of a situational semantic field, as well as taking into account the mass, features culture and even the way textual material is presented.

Thus, discourse analysis in teaching provides an opportunity to stimulate students to self-study and the development of critical thinking, which is vital not only in all areas of academic education, but also for lifelong education in general.

References:

1. Abdijalilova Z. D. (2007). Formation of the discursive competence of law students in teaching writing in a foreign language. BBC 94 Z 40, (41-S),244.
2. A.A. Abdullayev. System of information and communication technologies in the education. Science and world International scientific journal 2 (№ 5),19-21
3. Акрамов, М.Р. (2013). Психологические аспекты формирования экологического сознания личности. Science and World,80.
4. Акрамов, М.Р. (2020). Талабаларда матнларниидрок этишда психоллингвистиканинг ўрни. Сўз санъати халқаро журнали, 3(3).
5. Бабанский Ю. К. Методы обучения в современной общеобразовательной школе. – 2-е изд., перераб. и доп. М: Просвещение,2009.
6. M.M.Mirgiyazova, B.I. Urunov, M.S. Saidova. The pedagogical conditions for effective training language teachers professional development new methods and technologies. - Theoretical & Applied Science, 2020, 04 (84), 2020. – P.1017-1019.
7. Миргиязова М. М. (2017). Innovative technologies in teaching English. Молодой ученый, (25),301-302.
8. Миргиязова, М. М. (2018). Использование информационных технологий впроцессе оценки юридической терминологии Молодой ученый, (21),481-483.
9. Миргиязова, М. М. (2018). The importance of teaching legal English. Молодой ученый, (32),94-95.
10. Yusupov O.N. Cognitive semantics in context. Wschodnioeuropejskie Czasopismo Naukowe 7 (2),84-87.
11. Юсупов О.Н. Ўзбек адабиётининг инглиз тилидаги таржималарининг лингвокогнитив тадқиқи. Сўз санъати халқаро журнали. 3 сон, 3 жилд. Б.102- 105.

12. Юсупов О.Н. Анализ проблемы стиля в художественном переводе. The Way of Science, 94.2014.
13. Юсупов О.Н. Специфика художественного перевода. Наука и Мир 2 (3),170
14. - 172. 2014.
15. Mirzaakhmedova M.Yu. Approaches to science and education in the east and in the west. International journal of science and research (ISSN2319-7067).
16. Zoyirova, D.A. (2018). Forming Discursive Competence of Law Students. Eastern European Scientific Journal,(6).
17. Zoyirova D.A. (2019). Effective teaching of the English language based on the communicative-cumulative method in the process of education using modern technologies. Сўз санъати халқаро журнали,1(5).
18. Zoyirova D.A. (2019). features of translation from English to Russian. Экономика и социум, (10),71-73.
19. Yuldashevna, M. M., & Abdijalilovna, Z. D. (2019). The impact of the East in Shakespeare's tragedies. Journal of Critical Reviews, 7(3),2020.
20. Формирование интеллектуальной готовности старшего дошкольника к учебе в школе. // Балтийский гуманитарный журнал. – 2013. – № 3. – С.5-7.
21. <https://art.tadqiqot.uz/index.php/art/article/view/215/214>
22. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajssei/Volume02Issue12-17>

